

REGIONAL FORECASTING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GRAPE AND WINE-MAKING INDUSTRY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract . Based on statistical data, the paper proposes a methodology for long-term and short-term forecasting, namely: the selection of factors, statistical data, their assessment, and others, taking into account regional characteristics of production and the needs of wine products in the foreign and domestic markets.

Keywords. Forecasting, regional peculiarities, wine production, planning, complex forecasting methodology, production cycle.

In modern Uzbekistan, major projects are being implemented to modernize industry and construction in accordance with the measures taken by the government further improving the efficiency of mechanisms for managing the implementation of state and regional programs. [1] The process of accelerated economic development of the state affects the improvement of management efficiency in each economic area and increases the degree of the need to use scientific management methodology in practice.

When implementing the production cycle, an important task is to improve the modeling and forecasting of scientific and technological progress at each level of economic management in the region, bringing them together in the Republic as a whole.

The often used long-term forecast of production activity makes it possible to determine with sufficient accuracy the usefulness, expediency, and effectiveness of current activities. Any forecasting process must be built in the context of the region of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the following sequence:

1. Formulation of the regional problem.
2. Collecting information and choosing a forecasting method.
3. Application of the method and evaluation of the obtained forecast.
4. Using the forecast to make a decision.
5. Analysis "forecast-fact".

Depending on the formulation of the problem, the task of forecasting for individual regions and for the country as a whole is determined. A feature of short-term production planning is that it is not important there, the volume of sales in the coming period. The most important is the most efficient distribution of the volume of production according to the available production capacities.

Forecasts are developed on the basis of studying the scientific, technical and economic problems of development at all levels of management. The solution of these problems depends on the development of forecasting methods and economic results obtained in the development of a comprehensive program for the development of the enterprise. When developing specialized software systems for development, it is very important to process

statistical information, which is carried out in conjunction with the creation of econometric models of the functioning of the industry.

A comprehensive program should include a set of activities for each stage of the production chain "growing - production - sale". But in reality, there is a possibility of a bottleneck in the production process. The development of forecasts for the development of the industry includes a comprehensive analysis and results of the activities and interactions of the stages of the production chain. The formation of a model for forecasting and analyzing the management of enterprises by region and in the industry as a whole is based on the level of implementation of the achievements of scientific and technological progress in a given region.

Improving the model of the production chain management system, it is necessary to follow those methodological principles of scientific and technical progress, the implementation of which should guarantee:

- completeness, reliability and objectivity of information;
- the feasibility and cost-effectiveness of the costs of creating a production model;
- availability of capacities for expansion and improvement of the system.
- the use of economic and mathematical models for forecasting and planning the development of science and technology in the region, as well as macro modeling of resource requirements and determining growth rates.

In particular, the forecast helps to determine the prospects and trends in the development of the wine industry, structural shifts in the harvesting of assortment grapes and the problems and tasks arising from this for the long-term and current planning and management of the wine industry. So in the wine industry, forecasting should be carried out in several directions:

- forecasting the volume of grape harvest;
- forecasting the volume of production of finished products;
- forecasting sales volumes of finished products;
- forecasting the financial income of the enterprise.

Forecasting the volume of harvesting grapes in the industry is the initial stage in the implementation of an integrated planning system for the wine industry.

Table 1

The relationship of grape harvest, production volume and sales volume of wine products [2]

	grape harvest		Volume of production of finished products		Volume of sales	
	Million tons	% to the previous year	Thousand gave	% to the previous year	Million sum	% to the previous year
2013	1322.1	109.6	884256	109.3	1376.6	
2014	1440.7	109	1116828.9	126.3	1417.9	103
2015	1579	109.6	1246034.4	111.6	1922.8	135
2016	1735.3	109.9	1394067.7	105.9	2341.7	121

The total area of vine plantations in the republic in 2016 amounted to over 131 thousand hectares. In Uzbekistan, the regions reproducing vineyards are divided into two groups: northern and southern .

table 2

Characteristics of the regional cultivation of grapes in some regions of the republic

[3]

No.	Region name	Planted area (ha) (2014)	Characteristics of the grown grapes
1	Samarkand region	38268 ha	It specializes in the production of table grapes and dried products - sultanas and raisins.
2	Tashkent region	14486 ha	The culture of table grapes is developed. In the foothills, local varieties are famous for making champagne wine materials.
3	Fergana region	4795 ha	The vineyards are mainly table, partly technical and raisins.

The country's largest grape sown areas in total account for more than 65% of all areas, in particular, in the Samarkand region (southern region) - 38.3 thousand hectares, in the Tashkent region (northern region) - 14.5 thousand hectares, in Surkhandarya regions (southern region) - 14.2 thousand hectares and in Namangan region (northern region) - 11.1 thousand hectares. At the end of 2016, more than 1,735 thousand tons of grapes were grown in the republic, while in the country the yield level in 2016 amounted to 141.9 centners per hectare.

Table 1 shows that in 2014 the volume of sales increased by 41.3 million soums. compared to the previous year; the same indicator in 2015 amounted to 504.9 million soums; and in 2016 by 418.9 million soums. Analysis of the data allows us to say that the grape harvest in 2017 can increase by at least 9%, but the volume of production and sales will be excellent. The process of corporate governance of a winery reflects the constant development of management decisions and their practical application. Their use of a comprehensive forecasting methodology will allow them to foresee and analyze situations, expected long-term and current results, as well as the development trend in the future. It is advisable in the production cycle "growing-processing-sale" to use a comprehensive forecasting methods using the achievements of scientific and technical progress. We believe that the introduction of the ERP system at the enterprises of the wine industry will improve the quality of the forecast and prevent unforeseen problems in production.

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